

CO2LOGIX: A first-order model of pressure-constrained CO₂ geological storage growth at the basin scale

Iain de Jonge-Anderson^{a,*}, Gareth Johnson^b, Juan Alcalde^c, Jennifer J. Roberts^a

^a Department of Civil & Environmental Engineering, University of Strathclyde, Glasgow, UK

^b Drax Group, Drax Power Station, Selby, North Yorkshire, UK

^c Geosciences Barcelona (GEO3BCN), CSIC, Barcelona, Spain

ARTICLE INFO

Dataset link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17484441>

Keywords:

CO₂ storage capacity
Injectivity
CCS growth
Pressure response
Simplified models

ABSTRACT

Subsurface pressure increases from CO₂ injection can constrain injectivity and operating margins, reducing the dynamic capacity of CO₂ geological storage systems. Engineered pressure management approaches are effective but carry additional cost and risk. Understanding the magnitude, interaction and evolution of these effects at the regional and multi-project scale is limited by computational demands and uncertainty over future deployment trajectories. This presents a limitation for climate-policy-informing frameworks such as Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs), which typically consider only static capacity in carbon capture and storage technology growth. We present CO2LOGIX, a new model which evaluates the scale of subsurface pressure buildup under different growth trajectories with computational efficiency. The model combines well-established analytical solutions describing pressure diffusion in the subsurface with a flexible logistic growth model, which informs well deployment rates and can be adjusted to reflect realistic development scenarios. We demonstrate the value of CO2LOGIX through a UK case study. In a modelled scenario based on historic industry growth rates, unmitigated pressure reaches upper bounds after 83 years, with ~ 12 GtCO₂ stored by 2100 – well above national targets of 4–6 GtCO₂. However, short-term storage rates remain low (5 MtCO₂/year by 2030 and 30 MtCO₂/year by 2050), below recommended targets. Faster growth scenarios cause earlier pressure limit breaches, reducing available unmitigated capacity or requiring costly mitigation. Our findings underscore the importance of incorporating realistic pressure feedbacks between injection rates and long-term storage capacity into IAMs. CO2LOGIX provides a new first-order framework to anticipate and manage pressure limits in large-scale CO₂ storage deployment.

1. Introduction

The storage of CO₂ within deep geological formations (CO₂ geological storage; CGS) is a low-carbon technology that is essential for achieving climate objectives. However, these objectives can only be met if deployment of the technology scales up rapidly (IPCC, 2022), requiring that a number of barriers are overcome. These barriers span issues of public acceptance, the presence of viable business models and the establishment of consistent regulation, as well as subsurface-related challenges, including uncertainty in geological storage capacity (Krevor et al., 2023; Lane et al., 2021).

Geological storage capacity is controlled by both static and dynamic constraints. Static capacity is independent of time and is considered a representation of the total volume of pore space that CO₂ could

theoretically fill within a storage formation. First-order estimates of static capacity can be readily made if the dimensions and basic geological properties of the storage formation are known (Bachu et al., 2007) and to an extent, some dynamic effects within saline aquifers can be approximated using storage efficiency factors (Bachu, 2015). Dynamic capacity, however, seeks to incorporate the time-varying effects of injection into a storage formation – including pressure response (how subsurface fluid pressure changes when CO₂ is injected into the subsurface), injectivity changes and geomechanical response. It is also sensitive to aboveground factors such as development strategy and the availability of CO₂ supply (Lane et al., 2021).

Pressure increases in the subsurface can lead to several unwanted outcomes including the displacement of saline brines towards sensitive receptors (such as groundwater aquifers) (Smye et al., 2024), fracturing

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: iain.de-jonge-anderson@strath.ac.uk (I. de Jonge-Anderson).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2026.104608>

Received 31 October 2025; Received in revised form 2 February 2026; Accepted 5 February 2026

Available online 12 February 2026

1750-5836/© 2026 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

of the caprock and overburden (Ringrose et al., 2013) and induced seismicity (Hennings et al., 2019). However, it is also closely monitored and regulated, meaning that projects operate within a defined pressure threshold. This threshold constrains dynamic storage capacity as operators would be required to decrease injection rates or ultimately cease operations once the threshold is reached.

If there is a high degree of conductivity across the storage formation, pressure propagation can occur over large distances (10 s – 100 s km), beyond the actual extent of the CO₂ plume, and possibly across different storage projects (Wijaya et al., 2022). Understanding the scale and consequences of this is crucial (Lane et al., 2021; Szulczewski et al., 2012). Studies utilising numerical modelling have demonstrated that basin-scale pressure buildup can substantially limit dynamic capacity, often to a fraction of static capacity (Anderson and Jahediesfanjani, 2019; Birkholzer and Zhou, 2009; Thibeau et al., 2014; Wijaya et al., 2024). The utility of numerical simulations is their ability to capture dynamic fluid behaviour and detailed, 3D geological models, yet this comes at the expense of large data requirements and simulation time. Introducing assumptions about geological properties and fluid behaviour such as the use of vertical-equilibrium modelling, reduce simulation runtimes and permit basin-scale analysis (Bandilla and Celia, 2017; Bandilla et al., 2019; Elenius et al., 2018; Pettersson et al., 2022). However, these simulations still require spatially resolved geological parameters and numerical gridding, which can be prohibitive for rapid screening across many well configurations and uncertainty realisations.

When considering geographically extensive areas or scenarios where the uncertainty in parameter space warrants exploring, analytical approaches are generally favoured (Azizi and Cinar, 2013; De Simone et al., 2019; De Simone and Krevor, 2021; Dentz and Tartakovsky, 2009; Mathias et al., 2011, 2009; Nordbotten et al., 2005; Smith et al., 2025, 2024; Vilarrasa et al., 2010). There are two modelling tools that use analytical equations to predict pressure-constrained capacity for different well configurations. The first is CO2BLOCK (De Simone et al., 2019; De Simone and Krevor, 2021; Kivi et al., 2025; Smith et al., 2025, 2024), developed by Imperial College, and which uses analytical equations (Nordbotten et al., 2004, 2005) to estimate pressure-constrained capacity for different well spacings, where each well injects simultaneously. CO2BLOCK is available as an open access code repository written in the MATLAB programming language. It requires a simple set of input data relating to the basin (such as boundary conditions and size), aquifer properties (including depth, thickness, permeability and compressibility) and geomechanical criteria that influence the pressure limit. The second is EasiTool (Ganjdanesh and Hosseini, 2017, 2018; Gulf Coast Carbon Center, 2025; Wang et al., 2025; Wang and Hosseini, 2024), developed by Gulf Coast Carbon Center, and which utilises a different analytical solution (Azizi and Cinar, 2013). Unlike CO2BLOCK, EasiTool can also model pressure management using brine extraction wells (Ganjdanesh and Hosseini, 2018) and its effectiveness has also been demonstrated on the regional scale (Wang et al., 2025). However, its source code is not open access, limiting its incorporation into other modelling workflows.

In this work, we build on these contributions, notably CO2BLOCK, by, for the first time, combining a modified version of a well-established and validated analytical function with growth models that predict possible CGS drilling rates in a given region. This enables us to explore the interaction between CGS development strategies, injection capacity under pressure constraints and regional storage scenarios. We term this new pressure-growth model CO2LOGIX v1.0 (CO₂ Logistic Growth and Injection) (de Jonge-Anderson et al., 2025). In this study, we describe the CO2LOGIX model and apply it within a case study of saline aquifer storage formations on the United Kingdom Continental Shelf (UKCS). Although we apply CO2LOGIX here to generate new insights into the UK's long-term CO₂ storage ambitions, the modelling framework is readily transferable to other regions, and to global assessments, under simple assumptions about geology and deployment trajectories.

2. The CO2LOGIX model

2.1. Model framework

CO2LOGIX is a new first-order model designed to simulate basin-scale pressure evolution from the phased deployment of CO₂ injection wells (de Jonge-Anderson et al., 2025). The model is designed for efficiency and can simulate injection into multiple basins with runtimes typically under one minute. The modelling approach can be summarised as follows (Fig. 1), with detailed explanation of the parameters presented in the subsequent sections.

A: Case study parameters

1. Definition of growth parameters used to represent the trajectory of CGS development within the area of interest. We use a logistic growth model constrained using a growth rate (λ), midpoint year (t_m : the axis of symmetry of the logistic function – where growth is greatest) and the carrying capacity (L : the maximum number of wells that region/basin/aquifer can accommodate).
2. Definition of geological and geographical parameters describing the outlines of the storage formations.
3. Distribution of well coordinates. In CO2LOGIX v1.0, the total number of wells (as defined by the carrying capacity (see point 1)) are first distributed across the area as appropriate for the simulated scenario. In the case study within this study, the wells are distributed at random locations.

B: Growth model

Definition of simulation schedule. The logistic growth model is used to calculate the number of new injection wells to be simulated per year. Each well is assigned a fixed injection duration and rate as defined by the user. In the case study presented herein, we use 1 MtCO₂/year per well over 25-year duration, in alignment with planned injection rates at the Endurance storage site in the UK Southern North Sea (BP, 2022).

C: Injection model

Calculation of analytical terms. The model iterates over each (yearly) timestep defined in step 4. For each timestep, it identifies which wells are active, and for how long they have been injecting thus far. Properties that vary by storage formation (porosity, permeability, thickness, depth) are extracted by identifying which storage formation the well is positioned in and sampling these. Each storage formation is assumed to be hydraulically isolated, meaning that there is no pressure interference across formations (even if formations are positioned adjacent to each other).

Running analytical solution. The variables defined in step 5 are passed to the pressure analytical solution to define the pressure contribution for each active well in that timestep. To allow efficient computation, the entire grid is subsampled to only the area within the pressure influence radius and the pressure responses joined back to the original grid after calculation. This process is repeated for each well active during the timestep, and the pressure responses are summed to represent the pressure buildup from multiple wells.

Normalisation to fracture pressure. Fracture pressure is estimated using an empirical relationship (described further in Subsection 2.3). By normalising, we permit the relative comparison of storage formations at different depths. The final output is expressed as a percentage of fracture pressure.

2.2. Logistic growth model

A key feature of CO2LOGIX is the addition of a logistic growth model to define the number of new injection wells to simulate per year, according to a set of growth parameters. These models follow a sigmoid (S-shaped) curve that represents realistic stages of technology growth (Fig. 2):

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram depicting the framework of our pressure-growth model. The numbers denote modelling steps further described in the text. R: pressure influence radius, ψ : plume radius, r: radial distance from injection well, P_o/P_f (overpressure normalised to fracture pressure).

Fig. 2. Illustrative plot of the four growth phases that comprise a logistic growth curve for CO₂ injection. t_m : midpoint year.

- a) A formative stage characterised by slow growth, reflecting the early, limited uptake of a new technology.
- b) An acceleration stage where growth is approximately exponential as the technology gains wider adoption.
- c) A decelerating expansion stage as growth approaches saturation.
- d) A saturation phase where the growth rate declines to zero and the system reaches maximum capacity.

The output of the growth function at time, t , is expressed as:

$$f(t) = \frac{L}{1 + e^{-\lambda(t-t_m)}} \quad (1)$$

Eq. (1) can be fully characterised using three free parameters: L (carrying capacity), λ (logistic growth rate) and t_m (the midpoint of the function; the time of maximum growth). For the purposes of CO2LOGIX v1.0, the carrying capacity is the maximum number of wells achievable within the model domain (series of saline aquifers, or geological basins).

2.3. Pressure analytical model

We use a series of analytical functions to estimate single-well pres-

sure buildup with CO₂ injection. These functions derive from the work of Nordbotten et al. (2004, 2005) and have since been included in many works, including CO2BLOCK (De Simone et al., 2019; De Simone and Krevor, 2021; Kivi et al., 2025; Smith et al., 2025, 2024). The Nordbotten analytical solution allows rapid estimation of pressure evolution in a porous formation as a function of time, permeability, injection rate, and boundary conditions, without requiring full numerical simulation. We adopt the implementation described in De Simone et al. (2019) which can be summarised as four principal functions (Table 1). Note that a key assumption of this approach is that pressure buildup (ΔP) decreases logarithmically with radial distance (r) from the injection well, reaching zero at the pressure influence radius (R). The magnitude of ΔP is then a function of the characteristic pressure function (p_c):

$$p_c = \frac{Q\mu_w}{2\pi hk} \quad (2)$$

Hence, while the rate of pressure decay with distance is determined by pressure and plume radii (Table 1), the magnitude of pressure buildup is strongly dependent on volumetric flow rate (Q) and the thickness (h) and permeability (k) of the aquifer.

The functions described in Table 1 are used to calculate a single-well solution (Fig. 3a), for each active well at each timestep of the model. At each timestep, the simulation time t is increased by one for each active injection well. This allows scenarios to be explored where different wells start injecting at different times, a key difference between our implementation of this model and that developed in De Simone et al. (2019); De Simone and Krevor (2021). It should be noted that this approach is valid for situations only where ΔP is increasing and the pressure influence radius is expanding over time. This places a limitation on the current implementation of this model in that the injection rates cannot decline over time. Once a well stops injection, the time, t value associated with it is “frozen” to ensure its pressure contribution persists, but does not expand, in future timesteps.

At the end of each timestep, all pressure responses are summed to produce a composite, multi-well pressure response (Fig. 3b), before being normalised to fracture pressure (ΔP_n) as:

$$\Delta P_n = \frac{\Delta P + P_h}{P_f} \quad (3)$$

Where P_h is hydrostatic pressure and P_f is fracture pressure. We outline how we estimate P_f further in Subsection 3.1.1.

Table 1

A summary of the analytical equations used to estimate pressure buildup (ΔP).

Parameter	Function	Variables
Pressure influence radius (R)	$\sqrt{\frac{2.25kt}{c_{tot}\mu_w}}$	k : permeability (m ²), t : time (s), c_{tot} : total compressibility (Pa ⁻¹), μ_w : brine viscosity (Pa·s)
CO ₂ plume outer radius (ψ)	$\exp\left[\left(\frac{\mu_c + \mu_w}{\mu_c - \mu_w}\right)\ln\left(\sqrt{\frac{\mu_c}{\mu_w}}\right) - 1\right]\sqrt{\frac{Q\bar{\phi}}{\pi\phi h}}$	μ_c : CO ₂ viscosity (Pa·s), Q : volumetric flow rate (m ³ /s), ϕ : porosity (v/v), h : thickness (m)
Pressure buildup (ΔP) (open boundary)	$\frac{Q\mu_w}{2\pi hk} \left\{ \frac{\mu_c}{\mu_w} \ln\left(\frac{\psi}{r}\right) + \ln\left(\frac{R}{r}\right), r < \psi \right.$ $\left. \ln\left(\frac{R}{r}\right), \psi < r \leq R \right.$	r : radial distance from injection well (m)
Pressure buildup (ΔP) (closed boundary)	$\frac{Q\mu_w}{2\pi hk} \left\{ \frac{\mu_c}{\mu_w} \ln\left(\frac{\psi}{r}\right) + \ln\left(\frac{r_c}{\psi}\right) + \frac{2R^2}{2.25r_c^2}, r < \psi \right.$ $\left. \ln\left(\frac{r_c}{\psi}\right) + \frac{2R^2}{2.25r_c^2}, \psi < r \leq R \right.$	r_c : radius of pressure boundary (m)

While CO2LOGIX includes functions for both open and closed boundaries, our UKCS case study considers only open boundaries. Equations are adopted after De Simone et al. (2019).

3. Applying CO2LOGIX to assess pressure-growth-constrained capacity of UKCS saline aquifers

3.1. Case study model structure and constraints

We demonstrate the performance and utility of CO2LOGIX v1.0 using a case study focused on the UK, which we selected for its ambitious CGS targets and the availability of multi-basin scale geological datasets. The UK government is offering substantial support to deliver Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) clusters, matching capture projects with shared transport and storage infrastructure. These clusters will facilitate the decarbonisation of industrial regions of the UK, however there are also ambitions to potentially import captured CO₂ from Europe (Abel et al., 2025). The Climate Change Committee (CCC) recommends that if the UK's legislated carbon budgets and Nationally Determined Contributions are to be met, CGS associated with energy, industry and engineered removals should reach 73 MtCO₂/year in 2050, resulting in 1000 MtCO₂ of cumulative storage by 2050 (Climate Change Committee, 2025).

The case study focus is two-fold: to test and validate CO2LOGIX v1.0 and to explore the compatibility of technological growth rates on pressure buildup and, ultimately pressure-constrained capacity in UKCS storage formations. It was necessary to limit our analysis to only a subset of UKCS saline aquifers as CO2LOGIX v1.0 cannot currently accommodate stacked (i.e. overlapping) storage formations. To do this, we accessed databases of storage formations across Europe (GSEU Project, 2025; Poulsen et al., 2014) and extracted seven UK saline aquifer formations, adopting a selection strategy that prioritised shallower formations, and avoiding some hydrocarbon-bearing units such as the Permian units of the Southern North Sea and East Irish Sea. The saline aquifers selected for this study are summarised in Table 2 and Fig. 4.

3.1.1. Pressure space – the physical limit used in growth curves

We begin our analysis with an estimate of the upper limit on pressure-constrained capacity for each UKCS saline aquifer, assuming full utilisation is possible, up to the maximum allowable injection pressure. For each saline aquifer we calculate the mass of CO₂, M_{CO_2} , that can be stored in a pressure-constrained volume (Bump and Hovorka, 2024):

$$M_{CO_2} = V_p \Delta P C_t \rho_{CO_2} \quad (4)$$

Where V_p is the entire pore volume of the saline aquifer, ΔP is the allowable increase in pressure, C_t is total (rock and fluids) compressibility, and ρ_{CO_2} is the density of CO₂ calculated at subsurface conditions. The pore volume of each saline aquifer is calculated using area, thickness and porosity data held within GSEU Project (2025) and Poulsen et al. (2014). Total compressibility is calculated by first estimating rock compressibility from an empirical equation (determined under loading conditions) using porosity (Hall, 1953), and assuming pores are filled with brine (of 5×10^{-10} Pa⁻¹ compressibility). This is intended as a first-pass estimate, while acknowledging that compressibility under unloading (injection) conditions will likely be lower (Zheng and Espinoza, 2021). CO₂ density is estimated by using an equation of state (Bell et al., 2014) assuming the aquifer depths outlined in GSEU Project (2025), hydrostatic pressure, and a uniform geothermal gradient of 25 °C/km.

We also assume that maximum allowable pressure (P_{lim}) is 90 % of fracture pressure. This aligns with regulations adopted in the USA (Injection well operating requirements, 2025), however in the UK, such a limit is defined on a case-by-case basis (NSTA, 2025). In practice, P_{lim} may be further constrained by geomechanical and/or leakage risks such as outcropping aquifers, critically stressed faults or legacy well integrity; however, accounting for these risks was outside the scope of this study.

There are several approaches to estimate fracture pressure, including analysing leak-off tests (Zoback, 2007a), laboratory experiments and

Fig. 3. Illustrations of a single well (a) and multi-well (b) solution.

Table 2

Summary of the seven UKCS saline aquifers used as input to our test case for CO2LOGIX v.1.0 pressure-growth model.

Saline aquifer	Area (km ²)	Gross thickness (m)	Vertical net-to-gross (unitless)	Depth (m)	Porosity (unitless)	Permeability (mD)	Theoretical capacity (GtCO ₂) *	Pressure capacity (GtCO ₂)
Bunter Sandstone Formation	57,253.6	150	0.86	1535	0.15	20	618.3	5.0
Otter Sandstone Formation	6187.5	125	0.70	1500	0.17	50	51.0	0.4
St Bees Sandstone Unit	11,877.4	885	0.83	1435	0.09	5	427.5	3.8
Captain Sandstone Main	3438.0	123	0.90	900	0.31	7000	36.8	0.2
Mey Sandstone Unit	31,191.8	238	0.76	2300	0.26	500	888.9	10.2
Dornoch Formation	9371.2	300	0.20	1400	0.25	150	75.7	0.5
Heimdal Sandstone Unit	5925.4	492	0.75	1422	0.25	200	296.4	2.1
Totals	125,244.9						2394.6	22.2

Data is sourced from GSEU Project (2025) and Poulsen et al. (2014). Outlines of each aquifer are shown in Fig. 4. The pressure capacity shown in the final column is calculated using Eq. (4).

*Theoretical capacity is calculated as pore volume multiplied by CO₂ density.

analysis of petrophysical datasets (Zhang, 2011). However, these approaches require the acquisition and analysis of rock samples and/or wireline logging data, which is beyond the high-level focus of this case study. Instead, we adopted an empirical approach. From analysis of 229 leak-off-test datasets, Zhang and Yin (2017) discovered that fracture overpressure with respect to hydrostatic pressure, was, on average, 0.75 of the difference between hydrostatic (P_h) and lithostatic (P_l) pressure:

$$P_f = P_h + 0.75(P_l - P_h) \quad (5)$$

This empirical relation, described in Eq. (5), is adopted herein, where well-established gradients of P_h and P_l are set to 10 MPa/km and 23 MPa/km respectively (Zoback, 2007b). As the difference between P_h and P_l increases with depth, the difference between P_h and P_f also increases with depth; hence, provided all other parameters are equal, a shallower saline aquifer will reach P_f sooner than a deeper equivalent.

After following Eqs. (4) and 5, we calculate that the total pressure-constrained capacity of the seven UKCS saline aquifers is 22.2 GtCO₂. We consider this as the physical upper limit of the storage resource which we then use to define the carrying capacity of the logistic growth model. We also assume uniform injectivity of 1 MtCO₂/year and lifetime of 25 years per well, so to store 22.2 GtCO₂ would require drilling 880 wells.

3.1.2. Logistic growth scenarios

Given our interest in exploring the effect of growth trajectory on

pressure buildup, we model three possible growth scenarios for UK CGS development, each constrained by two fixed assumptions. Firstly, we assume that in the first modelled year (t1, 2026), only two CO₂ injection wells are drilled in the UKCS across all scenarios, reflecting one well per project selected for "Track 1" cluster sequencing in the UK. Secondly, we assume saturation at 880 wells, as calculated above. These assumptions allow the logistic function (Eq. (1)) to be rearranged to calculate the midpoint year for each scenario (Table 3).

Our modelling strategy then focuses on exploring three different growth scenarios parameterised using different logistic growth rates (Table 3; Fig. 5). The *Reference* growth scenario assumes a growth rate of 8.6 %; the rate observed by Zahasky and Krevor (2020). Under this scenario, saturation is not achieved by the end of the 100-year period (Fig. 5a). We then test two higher growth scenarios, both of which result in saturation within 100 years (Fig. 5b, c). Our *High* growth scenario assumes 13 % growth rate (the median logistic coefficient calculated from the analysis of the adoption of 148 unique technologies (Nemet et al., 2023)) and our *Very high* growth scenario assumes 22 % growth rate (the 75th percentile in logistic coefficient found from the same range of technologies (Nemet et al., 2023)). This latter, most optimistic growth scenario also corresponds, approximately, to the growth rate of hydrocarbon development in the Gulf of Mexico, which we estimate at 20 % based on data presented in Ringrose and Meckel (2019).

Fig. 4. Geographic outlines of the seven UKCS saline aquifers used as input to the pressure-growth model (left) and a bar chart depicting their pressure-constrained capacities (right) calculated using Eq. (4). Geological properties for each aquifer are summarised in Table 2.

Table 3
Summary of the three growth scenario parameters modelled for the UKCS case study.

Parameters	Reference growth	High growth	Very high growth
Logistic growth rate (%)	8.6 (Zahasky and Krevor, 2020)	13 (Nemet et al., 2023)	22 (Nemet et al., 2023)
Carrying capacity (L)	880	880	880
Number of wells in year 1 (2026)	2	2	2
Midpoint year (t _m) (calculated)	2097	2073	2054

The logistic growth rate of the Reference growth scenario is taken from observed growth in CCS capacity between 1997 and 2020 (Zahasky and Krevor, 2020). The 13 % and 22 % growth rates used within High and Very high growth scenarios correspond to the median and 75th percentile respectively in a study of logistic coefficients from various energy technologies (Nemet et al., 2023).

3.1.3. Example pressure responses for selected saline aquifers

Table 2 illustrates that the seven UKCS saline aquifers selected for this study possess contrasting geological properties, which we expect to translate into differing pressure responses to CO₂ injection. To explore this, we undertook a test model run using the High growth scenario described in Table 3 and Fig. 5. Fig. 6 presents pressure snapshots at the end of the modelled period, for selected saline aquifers, with all panels scaled equally in the horizontal (X-Y) dimensions.

For saline aquifers with moderate to low permeability and/or thickness, the pressure buildup remains spatially limited at this scale, with some regions remaining entirely unpressurised. This behaviour is particularly evident in the St Bees Sandstone Unit (Fig. 6a) where the pressure footprints are confined to a narrow radius around the injection wells. The Bunter Sandstone Formation (Fig. 6b), which has higher average permeability according to GSEU Project (2025) (Table 2), exhibits larger footprints and greater interference between wells, as well as greater pressure buildup around the wells themselves.

In contrast the Heimdal Sandstone Unit (Fig. 6c) and Mey Sandstone Unit (Fig. 6d) display a much more diffuse pressure response. In these cases, the entire saline aquifer becomes pressurised, albeit at very small magnitudes, with only moderate pressure buildup around the injection wells. This behaviour reflects the substantially higher average permeability and thickness of these aquifers compared with the St Bees Sandstone Unit and Bunter Sandstone Formation (Table 2). Note that the colour-scaling for the Mey Sandstone Unit in Fig. 6 is significantly compressed to visualise this response.

3.2. Results and implications for UK CGS targets

3.2.1. Pressure-growth-constrained capacity

Following a full suite of model runs, we observe that across the three growth scenarios we defined, median pressure buildup adopts a similar S-shaped trend to that of the logistic growth model, with higher growth rates leading to faster rises in pressure. This is a somewhat expected result where pressure increase aligns well with injection growth. For our Reference growth scenario, subsurface pressure buildup rate is relatively gradual, and pressure remains below P_{lim} for most of this century (Fig. 7a). With higher growth rates, P_{lim} is reached earlier as the pressure buildup is more rapid, with the most extreme case resulting in P_{lim} reached by 2064 (Fig. 7e).

We consider pressure-growth-constrained capacity as the cumulative mass of CO₂ stored at the year P_{lim} is reached in that growth scenario. We find that despite the substantial difference in the number of injection wells simulated across each scenario, the pressure-constrained capacity remains relatively stable at between 10.5 and 12.3 GtCO₂ (Table 4). In fact, the greatest pressure-constrained capacity was found for the most conservative, Reference growth scenario, whereas for higher growth scenarios, the capacity is lower, despite the greater number of injection wells added to the model by the year P_{lim} is reached (Table 4). This is to some extent a feature of the model design, in which injection is halted immediately once P_{lim} is reached; in the high growth scenarios, many

Fig. 5. Plots of cumulative wells simulated over time for the three growth scenarios described in Table 3. L: carrying capacity, t_m : midpoint year, λ : logistic growth rate.

Fig. 6. Plots of pressure response (ΔP) at the end of a test model run using the Very high growth scenario described in Table 3 and Fig. 5. Note that each panel is scaled equally in terms of horizontal dimensions (X-Y) to allow visual comparison of pressure footprints. The colour scaling used to represent ΔP in panels (a)-(c) is also aligned, however, the scale used in (d) is significantly compressed.

wells therefore inject for only a few years, far below the typical lifetime of a storage facility.

3.2.2. Implications for CGS targets

Our modelling provides a conservative estimate of pressure-growth-

constrained capacity and identifies when further expansion would require active pressure management. The finding that 12.3 GtCO₂ could be stored by ~ 2100 within a subset of UKCS saline aquifers, under pressure constraints, and under realistic growth rates, is a very favourable result for the development of CGS in the UK. Long-term projections

Fig. 7. Plots of maximum P_o/P_f (overpressure normalised to fracture pressure) over time (left) and cumulative capacity over time (right) for three growth scenarios.

Table 4
Results of CO2LOGIX simulations for three growth scenarios defined for UKCS.

Growth scenario	Runtime per iteration (seconds)*	Year P_{lim} is exceeded (median)	Growth-constrained capacity (GtCO ₂)	Pressure-growth-constrained capacity† (GtCO ₂)	Cumulative wells at year P_{lim} is reached
Reference	~ 7	2109	21.5	12.3	648
High	~ 50	2085	23.2	11.7	727
Very high	~ 350	2064	23.7	10.5	792

Note that the runtime of each model iteration increases significantly with the number of wells simulated.

*Simulations were run on a laptop equipped with an Intel i9-14900HX CPU and 32 GB RAM.

†Pressure-growth-constrained capacity is defined as the cumulative capacity at the point the median model iteration reaches P_{lim} .

of CGS requirements in the UK are sparse, but if we adopt an indicative estimate of 4 to 5 GtCO₂ (Systemiq, 2025), our CO2LOGIX results suggest entirely sufficient storage requirements to fulfil these requirements, while potentially also offering spare resource for the EU export market. However, our results also indicate that pressure limits could be reached

at some locations, at around half of the total pressure-constrained capacity (Table 4). This behaviour highlights the strong influence of reservoir transmissivity, as saline aquifer permeability (although not a criterion for calculating pressure-constrained capacity) governs the rate and extent of pressure dissipation. As demonstrated in Eq. (2) and

Table 1, lower saline aquifer permeabilities will result in more elevated pressure buildup that is spatially constrained, which effectively reduces the accessible fraction of storage volume.

A notable feature of the CO2LOGIX simulations is the trade-off between injection growth rate and attainable capacity. While faster expansion achieves policy-relevant injection milestones earlier, it also accelerates pressure accumulation and shortens the operational life of many wells. This diminishing-returns behaviour underlines the importance of balancing deployment pace against pressure management to ensure sustainable storage performance. While our results suggest that the pressure-constrained capacity of even a subset of UKCS saline aquifers can be sufficient for long-term storage ambitions, they do point to potential issues in meeting short-term ambitions which stem from the trajectory of growth models. **Table 5** compares our CO2LOGIX model findings with the CGS requirements outlined by the CCC. We find that while no scenarios modelled resulted in P_{lim} being reached by 2050, only the *Very High* growth scenario resulted in both the annual and cumulative storage capacity recommended by the CCC being achieved by 2050 (**Table 5**). This suggests that while a *Reference* growth scenario might be entirely compatible with pressure constraints and long-term storage requirements, accelerated deployment would be needed to meet near-term policy milestones. This acceleration might benefit individual projects financially (as they expand capacity and in turn, profit) but at the expense of greater pressure interaction and a potential need for active management measures such as brine extraction or cross-formation pressure relief.

4. Discussion

4.1. The value of CO2LOGIX

CO2LOGIX demonstrates that large-scale, time-dependent assessments of geological storage can be achieved efficiently without compromising physical realism. Simulations involving up to 880 injection wells (**Table 3**), distributed across a total area of $\sim 125,000$ km² (**Table 2**), are completed in under six minutes per iteration (**Table 4**). The computational efficiency of CO2LOGIX allows multiple model iterations to be run per scenario, and while the case study we present focuses on the stochastic placement of wells, other parameters such as geological properties or injection rates can be defined by probability distributions. We extract first-order estimates of the bounds on pressure-constrained capacity that account for dynamic aquifer behaviour.

Our findings represent a further step in refining storage capacities of saline aquifers by explicitly linking dynamic capacity to industry growth. It is not unusual for capacity estimates to span orders of magnitude. The static capacity of the seven saline aquifers we study, calculated from pore space availability alone, is 2395 GtCO₂ (**Table 2**), yet when compressibility and allowable pressure limits are considered, the capacity reduces by a factor of 100 to 22.2 GtCO₂. When realistic growth trajectories are introduced through CO2LOGIX the effective capacity is further reduced by approximately half (**Table 4**), illustrating the role of temporal development and pressure feedbacks in defining

Table 5

The CGS targets depicted in the CCC's Balanced Pathway compared against CO2LOGIX model results for the three growth scenarios.

Metric	CCC Balanced Pathway	Reference growth	High growth	Very high growth
Per-year capacity at 2028 (MtCO ₂ /year)	5	3	3	3
Capacity at 2050 (MtCO ₂ /year)	73	29	57	303
Cumulative stored at 2050 (MtCO ₂)	1000	335	497	1876

usable storage.

Direct comparison of our case study findings with other work is made challenging by the fact that model constraints within CO2LOGIX v1.0 mean we can only consider a subset of storage options across the UK. However, our case study includes significant storage units at the forefront of CGS appraisal activities (such as the Bunter Sandstone, Captain Sandstone and Mey Sandstone), so therefore we do not anticipate our results drastically underrepresent UKCS storage options. Nevertheless, it remains that we observe capacities lower than those identified by other authors. The closest comparison to our study can be made with [Smith et al. \(2024\)](#) who use CO2BLOCK for predicting pressure buildup and estimated 71.2 GtCO₂ pressure-constrained capacity within the UK, close to the often-quoted 78 GtCO₂ value originally derived from CO2Stored ([Bentham et al., 2014](#)). The core difference between our modelling approach and that of [Smith et al. \(2024\)](#) is the consideration of growth trajectory, which itself provides a further constraint. However, the similarity between Smith and Bentham's results does attest to the utility of using analytical functions more generally to estimate injection dynamics and pressure-constrained capacity at scale.

4.2. Simplifying assumptions in CO2LOGIX

To maintain computational efficiency and model flexibility, CO2LOGIX incorporates several simplifying assumptions which we lay out and discuss in turn:

1. Subsurface pressure is permitted to rise unmitigated. In practice, interventions would likely be made to manage pressure response (e.g. re-directing CO₂ into adjacent storage formations ([Hansen et al., 2013](#); [Ringrose, 2020](#))).
2. Saline aquifers are represented as flat units with no-flow boundaries above and below. While this assumption is necessary to enable the utilisation of the analytical solution (**Table 1**), it neglects subsurface heterogeneity, and the role that semi-permeable top or base-seals could play in dissipating pressure vertically. Studies have shown that even micro-darcy permeability caprocks can substantially inhibit pressure buildup ([Vilarrasa and Carrera, 2015](#)). Assuming saline aquifers to be flat, by incorporating averaged depth input values (**Table 2**) also neglects the impact of subsurface topography in dictating pressure limits. In reality, the pressure limit of a dipping saline aquifer might be defined at its shallowest point.
3. Regions between injection wells are in perfect pressure communication. Using homogenous geological properties per aquifer assume pressure conductivity across that single aquifer. However, lithological (e.g. lateral changes in permeability) and/or structural (e.g. sealing faults) heterogeneities could lead to higher pressure buildup locally, but more restricted lateral pressure propagation.
4. Input parameters to the analytical solution are fixed for the simulation duration. This neglects dynamic changes to fluid parameters such as CO₂ compressibility and density, which are known to impact pressure buildup ([Vilarrasa et al., 2010](#)). It also enforces rigid assumptions about storage developments (i.e. fixed injection rates and lifespans per injection well). A more pragmatic and efficient approach to development might be to optimise rates and lifespans while keeping pressure within a defined threshold – however, our modelling approach cannot accommodate this currently.
5. We utilise one analytical function. Previous studies have evaluated and discussed in detail the accuracy of analytical solutions in approximating the results of numerical simulations ([De Simone et al., 2019](#); [Dentz and Tartakovsky, 2009](#); [Lu et al., 2009](#); [Vilarrasa et al., 2010](#)). The solution implemented in CO2LOGIX was found to be more accurate when viscous forces dominate ([Vilarrasa et al., 2010](#)), typically near the injection well and/or layered systems ([Ringrose and Bentley, 2021](#)), whereas the solution of [Dentz and Tartakovsky \(2009\)](#) was found to be more accurate when gravity forces dominate, typically further from the well and/or if gravity effects override the

effect of geological layering (Ringrose and Bentley, 2021). Ultimately, no two analytical solutions produce the same results, and different geological and injection scenarios require use of different formulations.

4.3. Sensitivity analysis

We undertook a sensitivity analysis to explore the extent to which CO2LOGIX input parameters influence modelled CGS capacity. We tested a range of input properties known to be critical to the core analytical functions (Table 1): permeability, depth, thickness, porosity and compressibility. In addition, we examined the sensitivity to the selected pressure limit. A one-at-a-time sensitivity analysis was performed, in which a reference case was first modelled and the model subsequently re-run multiple times with each parameter individually adjusted by $\pm 25\%$ relative to the reference value. As permeability is a strongly non-linear parameter, it was instead varied by a factor of 10 (Table 6).

Permeability, pressure limit, depth and thickness exert a strong control on modelled CGS capacity, whereas porosity and compressibility are comparatively less influential (Fig. 8). This is somewhat aligned with earlier observations that the input permeability and thickness values chosen result in vastly different pressure footprints and buildup (Fig. 6). In the reference case, 5.7 GtCO₂ is injected before the pressure limit is reached and injection is terminated. However, increasing permeability by a factor of 10, increases this capacity by approximately 300% (10 GtCO₂) as enhanced transmissivity leads to reduced pressure buildup and delays breaching of the pressure limit. This acute sensitivity – particularly on a geological property that is historically difficult to constrain – highlights the importance of modelling tools that can accommodate uncertainty analysis and explore a range of plausible geological scenarios. Similarly, the choice of pressure limit is likely to vary substantially between projects, depending on perceived risks such as the reactivation of faults and fractures. The sensitivity of model outcomes to this parameter further suggests that, for simplified modelling tools such as CO2LOGIX to provide meaningful insights, probabilistic input assumptions should be explored. While CO2LOGIX v1.0 accounts for some uncertainty through varying well placements, the incorporation of additional probabilistic inputs remains a subject for further development.

It is also important to note that compressibility and porosity do not significantly influence this model configuration because the analytical functions assume that the pressure influence radius around each well is fully open in terms of pressure communication. Under alternative modelling approaches that are more representative of closed or semi-closed boundary systems, compressibility in particular would be expected to play a more significant role. Furthermore, both porosity and compressibility are key inputs to the methodology used to calculate the upper bound on pressure-limited storage capacity (Eq. (4)). As such, while they are not dominant sensitivities within the analytical functions themselves, they do influence other aspects of this work.

4.4. Areas for further work

CO2LOGIX is designed as a first-order model to provide computationally efficient insights into pressure buildup for given CGS growth

Table 6

Summary of the input ranges to the one-at-a-time sensitivity analysis.

Parameter	Low	Reference	High
Porosity (unitless)	0.11	0.15	0.19
Thickness (m)	37.5	50	62.5
Permeability (mD)	10	100	1000
Depth (m)	1125	1500	1875
Compressibility (Pa ⁻¹)	3.8×10^{-10}	5×10^{-10}	6.3×10^{-10}
Pressure limit (% P _f)	60	80	100

Fig. 8. Tornado plot presenting the results of a one-at-a-time sensitivity analysis. The parameter ranges are described in Table 6. Δ Capacity refers to the change in storage capacity from the reference case result (5.7 GtCO₂).

scenarios, ultimately assessing the compatibility of different growth rates with storage capacity ambitions. The simplicity offered by CO2LOGIX is achieved by making a series of simplified assumptions which ensures the model remains lightweight to generate quick insights over large geographic areas and technology growth timescales. Such approaches are key for modelling frameworks such as Integrated Assessment Models, which typically seek a range of constraints that can be adjusted according to the scenario being modelled.

We acknowledge further areas of improvement that could be targeted in subsequent versions (hence our use of a versioning convention, e.g. CO2LOGIX v1.0). Including alternative analytical solutions (e.g. Azizi and Cinar, (2013); Dentz and Tartakovsky, (2009)) would enable testing of how different physical simplifications influence model outcomes. Developing model capability to adjust to pressure buildup (such as by tweaking future well positioning or through approximating pressure relief via brine production wells) could also be investigated. It is also recognised that defining fixed injection rates may not reflect reality and incorporating pressure-informed dynamic injection rates (e.g. after Ringrose and Meckel (2019)) could be an area for further improvement. Further development of CO2LOGIX will focus on areas such as these, but it is also important to keep sight of the advantages (simplicity, efficiency and flexibility) of this modelling approach and not sacrifice these to try and reproduce more robust simulation approaches.

5. Conclusions

We present a new computationally fast and light model called CO2LOGIX which is designed to estimate pressure buildup associated with CO₂ injection for different industry growth trajectories. We apply this model to a UK case study; utilising known saline aquifer characteristics and growth scenarios grounded on trends of technology adoption. Our results suggest that a reasonable estimate of a pressure-constrained CGS capacity for the UK is 12.3 GtCO₂, as this reflects historical growth rates and modest pressure buildup, with P_{lim} being reached, unmitigated, by 2109. This result is, however, acutely sensitive to several geological input parameters, particularly permeability, and future work should therefore explore alternative but plausible geological scenarios to better constrain this uncertainty. Notwithstanding this sensitivity, this estimated capacity comfortably exceeds the UK's anticipated storage requirement of 4–6 GtCO₂ this century, suggesting scope for offering surplus capacity for export. Although demonstrated here for the UK, CO2LOGIX is readily adaptable to other regions and scales, providing a computationally efficient way to explore how deployment strategies and pressure constraints shape long-term storage

ambitions.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT in order to highlight spelling, grammar and sentence structure improvements. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Iain de Jonge-Anderson: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Gareth Johnson:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Juan Alcalde:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Jennifer J. Roberts:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101081521 - UPTAKE - Bridging current knowledge gaps to enable the UPTAKE of carbon dioxide. JA acknowledges funding from Grant PID2022-140850BC22 funded by the Spanish MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by "ERDF/EU".

Data availability

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17484441> (The data and model code is available at)

References

Abel, L., Pearce, J., Akhurst, M., Kirk, K., Morris, H., Williams, J., 2025. Quantification of the UK CO₂ storage export potential for a carbon capture and storage service. <https://idric.org/resources/report-quantification-of-the-uk-co2-storage-export-potential-for-a-carbon-capture-and-storage-service/>.

Anderson, S.T., Jahediesfanjani, H., 2019. Estimating the pressure-limited dynamic capacity and costs of basin-scale CO₂ storage in a saline formation. *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 88, 156–167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2019.05.031>.

Azizi, E., Cinar, Y., 2013. A new mathematical model for predicting CO₂ injectivity. *Energy Procedia* 37, 3250–3258. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2013.06.212>.

Bachu, S., Bonijoly, D., Bradshaw, J., Burruss, R., Holloway, S., Christensen, N.P., Mathiassen, O.M., 2007. CO₂ storage capacity estimation: methodology and gaps. *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 1 (4), 430–443. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1750-5836\(07\)00086-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1750-5836(07)00086-2).

Bachu, S., 2015. Review of CO₂ storage efficiency in deep saline aquifers. *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 40, 188–202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2015.01.007>.

Bandilla, K.W., Celia, M.A., 2017. Active pressure management through brine production for basin-wide deployment of geologic carbon sequestration. *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 61, 155–167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2017.03.030>.

Bandilla, K.W., Guo, B., Celia, M.A., 2019. A guideline for appropriate application of vertically-integrated modeling approaches for geologic carbon storage modeling. *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 91, 102808. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2019.102808>.

Bell, I.H., Wronski, J., Quoilin, S., Lemort, V., 2014. Pure and pseudo-pure fluid thermophysical property evaluation and the open-source thermophysical property library CoolProp. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 53 (6), 2498–2508. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie4033999>.

Bentham, M., Mallows, T., Lowndes, J., Green, A., 2014. CO₂ STORage Evaluation Database (CO₂ Stored). The UK's online storage atlas. *Energy Procedia* 63, 5103–5113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2014.11.540>.

Birkholzer, J.T., Zhou, Q., 2009. Basin-scale hydrogeologic impacts of CO₂ storage: capacity and regulatory implications. *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 3 (6), 745–756. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2009.07.002>.

Bp, 2022. Endurance Storage Development Plan. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/629525a0d3bf7f036750aff5/NS051-SS-REP-000-00010-Storage_Development_Plan.pdf.

Bump, A.P., Hovorka, S.D., 2024. Pressure space: the key subsurface commodity for CCS. *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 136, 104174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2024.104174>.

Center, Gulf Coast Carbon, 2025. EASITool 5.1. Retrieved 8th January from. <https://gcc.beg.utexas.edu/easitool/>.

Committee, Climate Change, 2025. The Seventh Carbon Budget: Advice for the UK Government. <https://www.theccc.org.uk/publication/the-seventh-carbon-budget/>.

de Jonge-Anderson, I., Johnson, G., Alcalde, J., Roberts, J.J., 2025. iaindejongeanderson/CO2LOGIX: UK case study release (v1.0) (Zenodo). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17484441>.

De Simone, S., Krevor, S., 2021. A tool for first order estimates and optimisation of dynamic storage resource capacity in saline aquifers. *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 106, 103258. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2021.103258>.

De Simone, S., Jackson, S.J., Krevor, S., 2019. The error in using superposition to estimate pressure during multisite subsurface CO₂ storage. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 46 (12), 6525–6533. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019gl082738>.

Dentz, M., Tartakovsky, D.M., 2009. Abrupt-interface solution for carbon dioxide injection into porous Media. *Transp. Porous. Media* 79 (1), 15–27. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11242-008-9268-y>.

Elenius, M., Skurtveit, E., Yarushina, V., Baig, I., Sundal, A., Wangen, M., Landschulze, K., Kaufmann, R., Choi, J.C., Hellevang, H., Podladchikov, Y., Aavatsmark, I., Gasda, S.E., 2018. Assessment of CO₂ storage capacity based on sparse data: skade Formation. *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 79, 252–271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2018.09.004>.

Ganjdanesh, R., Hosseini, S.A., 2017. Geologic carbon storage capacity estimation using enhanced Analytical Simulation Tool (EASITool). *Energy Procedia* 114, 4690–4696. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2017.03.1601>.

Ganjdanesh, R., Hosseini, S.A., 2018. Development of an analytical simulation tool for storage capacity estimation of saline aquifers. *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 74, 142–154. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2018.04.017>.

GSEU Project, 2025. Map of CO₂ storage potential areas (formation, units and traps) at the EU-scale (Version 1). <https://www.europe-geology.eu/data-tools/map-viewer/>.

Hall, H.N., 1953. Compressibility of reservoir rocks. *J. Petrol. Technol.* 5 (01), 17–19. <https://doi.org/10.2118/953309-G>.

Hansen, O., Gilding, D., Nazarian, B., Osdal, B., Ringrose, P., Kristoffersen, J.-B., Eiken, O., Hansen, H., 2013. Snøhvit: the history of injecting and storing 1 Mt CO₂ in the Fluvial Tubåen Fm. *Energy Procedia* 37, 3565–3573. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2013.06.249>.

Hennings, P.H., Lund Snee, J.E., Osmond, J.L., DeShon, H.R., Dommissie, R., Horne, E., Lemons, C., Zoback, M.D., 2019. Injection-induced seismicity and fault-slip potential in the Fort Worth basin. *Bull. Seismol. Soc. Am.* 109 (5), 1615–1634. <https://doi.org/10.1785/0120190017>.

Injection well operating requirements, 2025. Washington, DC: U.S. Government Publishing Office retrieved from. <https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-D/part-146/subpart-H/section-146.88>.

IPCC, 2022. Climate Change 2022: mitigation of Climate change. In: Shukla, P.R., Skea, J., Slade, R., Khouardjajie, A.A., Diemen, R.v., McCollum, D., Pathak, M., Some, S., Vyas, P., Fradera, R., Belkacemi, M., Hasija, A., Lisboa, A., Luz, S., Malley, J. (Eds.), Contribution of Working Group III to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel On Climate Change. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009157926>. Eds.

Kivi, I.R., De Simone, S., Krevor, S., 2025. A simplified physics model for estimating subsurface CO₂ storage resources constrained by fault slip potential. *J. Rock Mech. Geotech. Eng.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrmge.2025.06.031>.

Krevor, S., de Coninck, H., Gasda, S.E., Ghaleigh, N.S., de Gooyert, V., Hajibeygi, H., Juanes, R., Neufeld, J., Roberts, J.J., Swennenhuis, F., 2023. Subsurface carbon dioxide and hydrogen storage for a sustainable energy future. *Nat. Rev. Earth Environ.* 4 (2), 102–118. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-022-00376-8>.

Lane, J., Greig, C., Garnett, A., 2021. Uncertain storage prospects create a conundrum for carbon capture and storage ambitions. *Nat. Clim. Chang.* 11 (11), 925–936. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-021-01175-7>.

Lu, C., Lee, S.-Y., Han, W.S., McPherson, B.J., Lichtner, P.C., 2009. Comments on "Abrupt-interface solution for carbon dioxide injection into porous Media" by M. Dentz and D. Tartakovsky. *Transp. Porous. Media* 79 (1), 29–37. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11242-009-9362-9>.

Mathias, S.A., Hardisty, P.E., Trudell, M.R., Zimmerman, R.W., 2009. Approximate solutions for pressure buildup during CO₂ injection in Brine aquifers. *Transp. Porous. Media* 79 (2), 265–284. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11242-008-9316-7>.

Mathias, S.A., González Martínez de Miguel, G.J., Thatcher, K.E., Zimmerman, R.W., 2011. Pressure buildup during CO₂ injection into a closed brine aquifer. *Transp. Porous. Media* 89 (3), 383–397. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11242-011-9776-z>.

Nemet, G., Greene, J., Müller-Hansen, F., Minx, J.C., 2023. Dataset on the adoption of historical technologies informs the scale-up of emerging carbon dioxide removal measures. *Commun. Earth. Environ.* 4 (1), 397. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-023-01056-1>.

Nordbotten, J.M., Celia, M.A., Bachu, S., 2004. Analytical solutions for leakage rates through abandoned wells. *Water. Resour. Res.* 40 (4). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2003wr002997>.

- Nordbotten, J.M., Celia, M.A., Bachu, S., 2005. Injection and storage of CO₂ in deep saline aquifers: analytical solution for CO₂ plume evolution during Injection. *Transp. Porous. Media* 58 (3), 339–360. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11242-004-0670-9>.
- NSTA, 2025. *Guidance on Applications for a Carbon Storage Permit: Version 3*.
- Pettersson, P., Tveit, S., Gasda, S.E., 2022. Dynamic estimates of extreme-case CO₂ storage capacity for basin-scale heterogeneous systems under geological uncertainty. *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 116, 103613. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2022.103613>.
- Poulsen, N., Holloway, S., Neele, F., Smith, N., Kirk, K., 2014. *CO2StoP Final report. GEUS: Copenhagen, Denmark*.
- Ringrose, P.S., Bentley, M., 2021. *Reservoir Model Design: A Practitioner's Guide (2 ed.)*. Springer, Cham. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-70163-5>.
- Ringrose, P.S., Meckel, T.A., 2019. Maturing global CO₂ storage resources on offshore continental margins to achieve 2DS emissions reductions. *Sci. Rep.* 9 (1), 17944. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-54363-z>.
- Ringrose, P.S., Mathieson, A.S., Wright, I.W., Selama, F., Hansen, O., Bissell, R., Saoula, N., Midgley, J., 2013. The In Salah CO₂ Storage Project: lessons learned and knowledge transfer. *Energy Procedia* 37, 6226–6236. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2013.06.551>.
- Ringrose, P., 2020. *How to Store CO₂ Underground: Insights from Early-Mover CCS Projects (1 ed.)*. Springer, Cham. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-33113-9>.
- Smith, A., Hampson, G., Krevor, S., 2024. Global analysis of geological CO₂ storage by pressure-limited injection sites. *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 137, 104220. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2024.104220>.
- Smith, A., Hampson, G., Kivi, I.R., Krevor, S., 2025. Carbon dioxide plumes, pressure space and legacy well risk for Southern North Sea CO₂ Storage projects. *Energy Geosci.*, 100475 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engeos.2025.100475>.
- Smye, K.M., Yut, K., Reedy, R.C., Scanlon, B.R., Nicot, J.-P., Hennings, P., 2024. Challenges with managing unconventional water production and disposal in the Permian Basin. *Am. Assoc. Pet. Geol. Bull.* 108 (12), 2215–2240. <https://doi.org/10.1306/08082424025>.
- Systemiq, 2025. Delivering a rapid, orderly and just energy transition for the UK Continental Shelf. <https://www.systemiq.earth/resource-category/uk-continental-shelf/>.
- Szulczewski, M.L., MacMinn, C.W., Herzog, H.J., Juanes, R., 2012. Lifetime of carbon capture and storage as a climate-change mitigation technology. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 109 (14), 5185–5189. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1115347109>.
- Thibeau, S., Bachu, S., Birkholzer, J., Holloway, S., Neele, F., Zhou, Q., 2014. Using pressure and volumetric approaches to estimate CO₂ storage capacity in deep saline aquifers. *Energy Procedia* 63, 5294–5304. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2014.11.560>.
- Vilarrasa, V., Carrera, J., 2015. Geologic carbon storage is unlikely to trigger large earthquakes and reactivate faults through which CO₂ could leak. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 112 (19), 5938–5943. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1413284112>.
- Vilarrasa, V., Bolster, D., Dentz, M., Olivella, S., Carrera, J., 2010. Effects of CO₂ compressibility on CO₂ storage in deep saline aquifers. *Transp. Porous. Media* 85 (2), 619–639. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11242-010-9582-z>.
- Wang, Z.W., Hosseini, S., 2024. Advanced CO₂ Storage Capacity Estimation with EASiTool V.5 SPE/AAPG/SEG Carbon, Capture, Utiliz., Storage Conf. Exhib. <https://doi.org/10.15530/ccus-2024-4001383>.
- Wang, Z., Hosseini, S.A., Bump, A.P., 2025. Hub scale subsurface fluid injection of GCS and SWD wells: implications on inter-project interferences and regional pressure buildup. *Int. J. Greenh. Gas Control* 147, 104477. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2025.104477>.
- Wijaya, N., Vikara, D., Morgan, D., Grant, T., & Remson, D. (2022). *Basin management of geologic CO₂ storage: effect of well spacing on CO₂ plume and pressure interference* SPE Western regional meeting. <https://doi.org/10.2118/209283-MS>.
- Wijaya, N., Morgan, D., Vikara, D., Grant, T., Liu, G., 2024. Dynamic modeling studies of basin-scale pressure interference and CO₂ plume evolution in multi-well geologic CO₂ storage. *Gas Sci. Eng.* 130, 205422. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jgsce.2024.205422>.
- Zahasky, C., Krevor, S., 2020. Global geologic carbon storage requirements of climate change mitigation scenarios [10.1039/D0EE00674B]. *Energy Environ. Sci.* 13 (6), 1561–1567. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D0EE00674B>.
- Zhang, J., Yin, S.-X., 2017. Fracture gradient prediction: an overview and an improved method. *Pet. Sci.* 14 (4), 720–730. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12182-017-0182-1>.
- Zhang, J., 2011. Pore pressure prediction from well logs: methods, modifications, and new approaches. *Earth. Sci. Rev.* 108 (1), 50–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2011.06.001>.
- Zheng, X., Espinoza, D.N., 2021. Measurement of unloading pore volume compressibility of frio sand under uniaxial strain stress path and implications on reservoir pressure management. *Rock. Mech. Rock. Eng.* 54 (11), 5745–5760. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00603-021-02571-3>.
- Zoback, M.D., 2007a. Determination of S₃ from mini-fracs and extended leak-off tests and constraining the magnitude of SH_{max} from wellbore failures in vertical wells. In (Ed.). In: Zoback, M.D. (Ed.), *Reservoir Geomechanics*. Cambridge University Press, pp. 206–234. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511586477.008>.
- Zoback, M.D., 2007b. Pore pressure at depth in sedimentary basins. In (Ed.). In: Zoback, M.D. (Ed.), *Reservoir Geomechanics*. Cambridge University Press, pp. 27–55. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511586477.003>.